

Prevalence and Economic Implications of Cattle Fetal Wastage at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Received 25 September, 2025, Accepted 10 October, 2025, Published 30 October, 2025

This study determined the prevalence and economic implications of cattle fetal wastage at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Over a three-month period, 1,602 cattle (1,515 cows) were examined post-mortem to detect pregnancy. Results revealed that 58 fetuses were recovered, giving a fetal wastage prevalence of 3.83%. The estimated economic loss was ₦4,712,500, based on the mean market value of calves in North Central Nigeria. Although seemingly small, this figure represents a substantial reproductive and financial loss to the livestock industry. The wastage contributes to herd depletion, reduced beef and milk output, and economic inefficiency. Contributing factors include inadequate ante-mortem inspection, weak regulation enforcement, and limited stakeholder awareness. The study concludes that fetal wastage undermines livestock sustainability and national food security. It recommends stricter veterinary inspection, awareness campaigns for butchers and herders, and supportive policies discouraging the slaughter of pregnant cows.

Keywords: Fetal wastage, cattle, prevalence, economic loss, abattoir, Nasarawa State.

INTRODUCTION

Cattle production plays a major role in Nigeria's agricultural economy, providing meat, milk, hides, and employment. Despite this importance, poor reproductive management and the indiscriminate slaughter of pregnant cows have contributed to fetal wastage — the loss of viable fetuses during slaughter.

Fetal wastage occurs due to weak ante-mortem inspection, limited veterinary presence, and socio-economic pressures that compel farmers to sell gravid animals. The result is a reduction in herd replacement, lower meat production, and economic losses. Given Nigeria's growing population and low animal protein intake, fetal wastage poses a serious threat to food security. This study aimed to determine the prevalence and economic consequences

of fetal wastage in cattle slaughtered at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, Nasarawa State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, located in Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The abattoir serves as the major meat processing center for Lafia and surrounding communities. A cross-sectional study was carried out over three months. Data were collected thrice weekly (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday) from slaughtered cattle.

Each slaughtered cow was examined post-mortem; the uterus was opened to determine pregnancy status, and fetuses were counted. Prevalence of fetal wastage was calculated as the number of fetuses recovered divided by the total number of cows slaughtered, multiplied by 100. Economic losses were estimated based on the average

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market value of a calf (₦81,250).

RESULTS

Out of 1,602 cattle slaughtered during the study, 1,515 were cows. Fifty-eight fetuses were recovered, representing a prevalence rate of 3.83%. At an estimated average market value of ₦81,250 per calf, the 58 lost fetuses translate into an economic loss of ₦4,712,500. This figure excludes indirect losses such as reduced milk yield, breeding potential, and genetic improvement opportunities.

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of 3.83% recorded in this study indicates that fetal wastage occurs at the Lafia Modern Abattoir, though lower than values reported elsewhere in Nigeria. Differences may be attributed to livestock source, pregnancy detection efficiency, or seasonality. The economic loss is significant, highlighting the negative impact on herd replacement and the livestock industry. Poor ante-mortem inspection, lack of pregnancy detection, and ignorance among butchers are major causes. Socio-economic pressures and festive demands also contribute to the sale of pregnant cows.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms the occurrence of fetal wastage at the Lafia Modern Abattoir with a prevalence of 3.83%, translating to an estimated economic loss of ₦4.7 million within three months. If unaddressed, this issue will continue to undermine livestock sustainability, meat production, and food security in Nasarawa State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Strengthen ante-mortem inspection to detect pregnancy before slaughter.
2. Educate herders, traders, and butchers on the long-term effects of fetal wastage.
3. Enforce policies against the slaughter of pregnant cows.
4. Increase veterinary presence in abattoirs.
5. Provide financial support for farmers to discourage distress sales of gravid cows.

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